

Covid-19 paper

Spectrum (MVP)

PXD019423=0

PXD019686

KADETQALPQR

KKADETQALPQR

ADETQALPQR

GFYAEGSR

EITVATSR

MSECVLGQSK

IAGHHLGR

QLQQSMSSADSTQA

ASANLAATK

SNLKPFER

CDIKDLPK

PXD020394

TATKAYNVTQAFGR

DGIWVATEGALNTPK

MAGNGGDAALALLLDR

QGTDYKHWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR

MAGDGGDAALALLLDR

MAGNGGDAALALLLDR

QKRTATKAYNVTQAFGR

PXD021328

DGIIWVATEGALNTPK

LDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK

AYNVTQAFGR

GQGVPI NTNSSPDDQIGYYR

HWPQIAQFAPSASAFF

KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

KADETQALPQR

ADETQALPQR

ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGER

LDDKDPNFK

IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK

LQDVVNQNAQALNTLVK

KKADETQALPQR

KSNLKPFER

LGTGPEAGLPYGANK

IAGHHLGR

DDKDPNFKDQVILLNK

FDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEK

FNGIGVTQNVLYENQK

GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR

GQGVPI NTNSSPDDQIGY

LQSLQTYVTQLIR

LTYTGAIK

GFQPTNGVGYQPYR

GPEQTQGNFGDQELTR

GGDAALALLLDR

IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK

LIANQFNSAIGK

Ions:
 a 1+ 2+ 3+
 b 1+ 2+ 3+
 c 1+ 2+ 3+
 x 1+ 2+ 3+
 y 1+ 2+ 3+
 z 1+ 2+ 3+
 MH 1+ 2+
 Internal
[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:
 H₂O (o)
 NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:
 Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:
 Most Intense
 Nearest

Match
 Peak Detect

Peak Labels:
 Ion m/z
 None

Width:
 Height:

b+	#	Seq#	y+
114.0913	1	L	12
227.1754	2	I	11
298.2125	3	A	10
412.2554	4	N	9
540.3140	5	Q	8
687.3824	6	F	7
801.4254	7	N	6
888.4574	8	S	5
959.4945	9	A	4
1072.5786	10	I	3
1129.6000	11	G	2
	12	K	1

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHGK

RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHGKEDLK

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

MAGNGGDAALALLLDR

MAGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLSK

RGPEQTQGNFGDQELTR

RPQGLPNNTASW

YLGTGPEAGLPYGANK

TALTQHGKEDLK

TALTQHGEDLK

PAADLDDFSK

VATEGALNTPK

WYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK

VAGDSGFAAYSR

YYLGTGPEAGLPYGANK

Ions:

a 1+ 2+ 3+

b 1+ 2+ 3+

c 1+ 2+ 3+

x 1+ 2+ 3+

y 1+ 2+ 3+

z 1+ 2+ 3+

MH 1+ 2+

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

b+	#	Seq#	y+
164.0706	1	Y 17	
327.1339	2	Y 16	1607.8064
440.2180	3	L 15	1444.7431
497.2395	4	G 14	1331.6590
598.2871	5	T 13	1274.6375
655.3086	6	G 12	1173.5899
752.3614	7	P 11	1116.5684
881.4040	8	E 10	1019.5156
952.4411	9	A 9	890.4730
1009.4625	10	G 8	819.4359
1122.5466	11	L 7	762.4145
1219.5994	12	P 6	649.3304
1382.6627	13	Y 5	552.2776
1439.6842	14	G 4	389.2143
1510.7213	15	A 3	332.1928
1624.7642	16	N 2	261.1557
	17	K 1	147.1128

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

SFIEDLLFNK

SMGTSPTRMAGNGGDAALALLLDR

NPANNAIVLQLPQGT

NTNSSPDDQIGYYR

NSSPDDQIGYYR

PXD023016

GIIVWATEGALNTPK

IIWVATEGALNTPK

IWVATEGALNTPK

VATEGALNTPK

DGIIVVATEGALNTPKG

WVATEGALNTPK

PXD024967

KADETQALPQR

KADETQALPQR

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

ADETQALPQR

QLQQSMSSADSTQA

PAADLDDFSK

ITFGGSDSTGSNQNGER

QLQQSMSSADSTQA

KADETQALPQR

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

QLQQSMSSADSTQA

ADETQALPQR

ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGER

PAADLDDFSK

QLQQSMSSADSTQA

PXD025214

LDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK

Ions:

a 1* 2* 3*

b 1* 2* 3*

c 1* 2* 3*

x 1* 2* 3*

y 1* 2* 3*

z 1* 2* 3*

MH 1* 2*

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width:

Height:

LDDKDPNFKDQVILLNK, MH+ 2015.0808

, Scan: Index=25890,POOLPOS-02.28438.28438.4

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
114.0913	1	L 17	
229.1183	2	D 16	1901.9967
344.1452	3	D 15	1786.9698
472.2402	4	K 14	1671.9428
587.2671	5	D 13	1543.8479
684.3199	6	P 12	1428.8209
798.3628	7	N 11	1331.7682
945.4312	8	F 10	1217.7252
1073.5262	9	K 9	1070.6568
1188.5531	10	D 8	942.5619
1316.6117	11	Q 7	827.5349
1415.6801	12	V 6	699.4763
1528.7642	13	I 5	600.4079
1641.8483	14	L 4	487.3239
1754.9323	15	L 3	374.2398
1868.9753	16	N 2	261.1557
	17	K 1	147.1128

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

RPQGLPNTASWFTALTQHGK

RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHGKEDLK

ITFGGPSDSTGSNQDGER

AYNVTQAFGR

ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGER

RPQGLPNNTASWF

Ions:

a 1+ 2+ 3+

b 1+ 2+ 3+

c 1+ 2+ 3+

x 1+ 2+ 3+

y 1+ 2+ 3+

z 1+ 2+ 3+

MH 1+ 2+

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width:

Height:

RPQGLPNNTASWF, MH+ 1487.7390

, Scan: index=33268, POOLPOS-01.36165.36165.2

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
157.1084	1	R	13
254.1612	2	P	12
382.2197	3	Q	11
439.2412	4	G	10
552.3253	5	L	9
649.3780	6	P	8
763.4209	7	N	7
877.4639	8	N	6
978.5116	9	T	5
1049.5487	10	A	4
1136.5807	11	S	3
1322.6600	12	W	2
	13	F	1

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

HWPQIAQFAPSASAFF

MAGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLESK

GQGVPIINTSSR

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

TALTQHGKEDLKFR

DGIIVVATEGALNTPK

GFYAEGRS

GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR

GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR

IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK

MAGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLESK

DRLNQLESK

GQGVPI NTNSSPDDQIGYYR

KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

RGPEQTQGNFGDQELTR

PGNGCDAALALLLDR

Ions:

a 1⁺ 2⁺ 3⁺

b 1⁺ 2⁺ 3⁺

c 1⁺ 2⁺ 3⁺

x 1⁺ 2⁺ 3⁺

y 1⁺ 2⁺ 3⁺

z 1⁺ 2⁺ 3⁺

MH 1⁺ 2⁺

Internal

[\(Deselect All\)](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width:

Height:

PGNGCDAALALLLDR, MH+ 1668.8738

, Scan: index=49160, POOLPOS-02.52891.52891.2

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
98.0600	1	P	16
155.0815	2	G	15
269.1244	3	N	14
326.1459	4	G	13
486.1765	5	C	12
601.2035	6	D	11
672.2406	7	A	10
743.2777	8	A	9
856.3618	9	L	8
927.3989	10	A	7
1040.4830	11	L	6
1153.5670	12	L	5
1266.6511	13	L	4
1379.7351	14	L	3
1494.7621	15	D	2
	16	R	1

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

Static Modifications:

C: 57.021464

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

Ions:

a 1+ 2+ 3+

b 1+ 2+ 3+

c 1+ 2+ 3+

x 1+ 2+ 3+

y 1+ 2+ 3+

z 1+ 2+ 3+

MH 1+ 2+

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest

Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width:

Height:

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK, MH+ 1844.9276

, Scan: index=51983, POOLPOS-03.55711.55711.2

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
112.0393	1	Q 17	
240.0979	2	Q 16	1733.8956
341.1456	3	T 15	1605.8370
440.2140	4	V 14	1504.7894
541.2617	5	T 13	1405.7209
654.3457	6	L 12	1304.6733
767.4298	7	L 11	1191.5892
864.4825	8	P 10	1078.5051
935.5197	9	A 9	981.4524
1006.5568	10	A 8	910.4153
1121.5837	11	D 7	839.3781
1234.6678	12	L 6	724.3512
1349.6947	13	D 5	611.2671
1464.7217	14	D 4	496.2402
1611.7901	15	F 3	381.2132
1698.8221	16	S 2	234.1448
	17	K 1	147.1128

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

Add to N-term: -17.026549

TQHGKEDLKFPF

YLTGPEAGLPYGANK

YLTGPEAGLPYGANK

WYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK

PXD026795

QYNVTQAFGR

Gamma

AYNVTQAFGR

RPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHGK

DGIWVATEGALNTPK

ADETQALPQR

DDQIGYYR

GEGVPINTNSSPDDQIGYYR

GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR

ITFGGPSDSTGSNQNGER

KADETQALPQR

RPQGLPNNTASWF

Delta

RPQGLPNTASWFTALTQHGK

AYNVTQAFGR

DGIWVATEGALNTPK

AYETQALPQR

GQGVPINTNSSPDDQIGYYR

LDDKDPNFK

GFYAEGSR

IAGHHLGR

IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK

ITFGGPDSTGSNQNGER

KAYETQALPQR

HWPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSR

KSNLKPFER

NSTPGSSMGTS PAR

Ions:

a 1+ 2+ 3+

b 1+ 2+ 3+

c 1+ 2+ 3+

x 1+ 2+ 3+

y 1+ 2+ 3+

z 1+ 2+ 3+

MH 1+ 2+

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width:

Height:

NSTPGSSMGTS PAR, MH+ 1349.6114

, Scan: index=6073, DELTA2_DDA.7115.7115.2

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
115.0502	1	N 14	
202.0822	2	S 13	1235.5685
303.1299	3	T 12	1148.5364
400.1827	4	P 11	1047.4888
457.2041	5	G 10	950.4360
544.2362	6	S 9	893.4145
631.2682	7	S 8	806.3825
762.3087	8	M 7	719.3505
819.3301	9	G 6	588.3100
920.3778	10	T 5	531.2885
1007.4099	11	S 4	430.2409
1104.4626	12	P 3	343.2088
1175.4997	13	A 2	246.1561
	14	R 1	175.1190

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

GPEQTQGNFGDQELIR

VAGDSGFAAYSR

LVDPQQLAVTR

YLGTPPEAGLPYGANK

VYSTGSNVFQTR

VTLADAGFIK

LGSPLSLNMAR

Omicron

AYNVTQAFGR

NPANNAIVQLPQGTTLPK

DGIWVATEGALNTPK

KADETQALPQR

Ions:

a 1+ 2+ 3+

b 1+ 2+ 3+

c 1+ 2+ 3+

x 1+ 2+ 3+

y 1+ 2+ 3+

z 1+ 2+ 3+

MH 1+ 2+

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest

Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width:

Height:

KADETQALPQR, MH+ 1256.6593

, Scan: index=4022, BD2BE2.5043.5043.2

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
129.1022	1	K 11	
200.1394	2	A 10	1128.5644
315.1663	3	D 9	1057.5273
444.2089	4	E 8	942.5003
545.2566	5	T 7	813.4577
673.3151	6	Q 6	712.4100
744.3523	7	A 5	584.3515
857.4363	8	L 4	513.3144
954.4891	9	P 3	400.2303
1082.5477	10	Q 2	303.1775
	11	R 1	175.1190

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

ITFGGSDSTGSNQNGGAR

QQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

HWPQJAFAPSASAFF

GQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYR

MAGNGGDAALALLLLDRLNQLSEK

TALTQHGKEDLK

KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK

Ions:

a 1+ 2+ 3+

b 1+ 2+ 3+

c 1+ 2+ 3+

x 1+ 2+ 3+

y 1+ 2+ 3+

z 1+ 2+ 3+

MH 1+ 2+

Internal

[\[Deselect All\]](#)

Neutral Loss:

H₂O (o)

NH₃ (*)

Mass Type:

Mono Avg

Mass Tol:

Peak

Assignment:

Most Intense

Nearest

Match

Peak Detect

Peak Labels:

Ion m/z

None

Width: 750

KQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSK, MH+ 1990.0491

, Scan: index=35742,BA2BB2.38391.38391.3

Click and drag in the plot to zoom X: Y: Enable tooltip

b+	#	Seq#	y+
129.1022	1	K 18	
257.1608	2	Q 17	1861.9542
385.2194	3	Q 16	1733.8956
486.2671	4	T 15	1605.8370
585.3355	5	V 14	1504.7894
686.3832	6	T 13	1405.7209
799.4672	7	L 12	1304.6733
912.5513	8	L 11	1191.5892
1009.6041	9	P 10	1078.5051
1080.6412	10	A 9	981.4524
1151.6783	11	A 8	910.4153
1266.7052	12	D 7	839.3781
1379.7893	13	L 6	724.3512
1494.8162	14	D 5	611.2671
1609.8432	15	D 4	496.2402
1756.9116	16	F 3	381.2132
1843.9436	17	S 2	234.1448
	18	K 1	147.1128

[\[Click\]](#) to move table

MAGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLESK

IGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIK

MAGDGGDAALALLLDR

WYFYLLGTGPEAGLPYGANK

